

Exploring the Role of NF-MQL in Sustainable Machining of Challenging Materials: A Review

Amol P Vadnere¹, Shyamkumar D Kalpande²,

Nandkishor O Warbhe³, Sachin B Mahale⁴,

^{1,2}PhD Research Scholar, Professor & Head, Department of Mechanical Engineering
MET's Institute of Engineering (SPPU) Nashik, India

^{3,4}Lecturer, Department of Mechanical Engineering, MET's Institute of
Technology-Polytechnic, Nashik, India

Abstract. Modern manufacturing industries are increasingly focused on achieving high quality, dimensional accuracy, surface finish, production efficiency, and cost reduction while minimizing environmental impact. Cutting fluids play a vital role in machining operations by cooling the cutting tool and workpiece, and by removing chips from the heat-affected zone. However, in high-speed machining, conventional fluid applications often fail to dissipate heat effectively, and their improper use and disposal adversely affect both human health and the environment. The Minimum Quantity Lubrication (MQL) technique offers a viable alternative, achieving effective cooling and lubrication using minimal quantities of lubricant. Recent studies have shown that combining MQL with nanofluids (NF-MQL) significantly enhances machinability and sustainability, particularly in the case of challenging materials. This paper presents a comprehensive review of the research on NF-MQL-assisted machining processes. The study concludes by identifying research gaps and proposing directions for future work in the field of sustainable machining.

Keywords: Difficult-to-cut materials, Minimum Quantity Lubrication (MQL), Nanofluid (NF), Sustainable Machining.

I. Introduction

In recent years, environmentally conscious machining practices have gained increasing attention in the manufacturing industry. Cutting fluids are widely used to enhance tool life and surface quality, but their extensive use poses significant health, economic, and environmental concerns. Approximately 85% of cutting fluids are mineral oil-based, and improper disposal without recycling leads to severe environmental pollution. Moreover, high treatment costs add to manufacturing expenses. Sustainability in machining has become a crucial requirement due to stricter environmental regulations, occupational safety norms, and the global demand for eco-friendly products. [8]

To meet these objectives, the reduction or elimination of conventional flood cooling systems has been widely investigated. However, the machining of advanced alloys—such as titanium, Inconel, and stainless steels—poses unique challenges due to their high strength, low thermal conductivity, and work hardening behaviour. These materials are categorised as difficult-to-cut because they generate excessive heat and tool wear during machining, often compromising productivity and surface integrity. In this context, Minimum Quantity Lubrication (MQL) offers a promising alternative. MQL minimizes coolant use by atomizing small amounts of lubricant into the cutting zone,

reducing friction and improving tool performance. The combination of MQL with nanofluids (NF-MQL) has emerged as an advanced cooling–lubrication technique to enhance both performance and sustainability in machining operations. [3]

II. MQL-Assisted Machining Of Challenging Materials

Machining operations such as grinding, turning, drilling, and milling are commonly used for shaping components with desired tolerances and surface finishes. However, when dealing with hard-to-machine materials, heat generation and friction at the tool–workpiece interface become critical challenges. High cutting temperatures lead to tool wear, dimensional inaccuracy, and reduced surface quality. [26]

Grinding is a finishing operation requiring precise control over temperature. Excessive heat can cause oxidation, metallurgical transformations, and surface burns. MQL has shown effectiveness in reducing grinding temperatures and improving surface integrity while significantly lowering fluid consumption. Turning, a fundamental machining process for cylindrical components, involves continuous tool–workpiece contact, resulting in high heat generation. The application of MQL effectively reduces cutting temperature, tool wear, and surface roughness by maintaining a thin lubricating film at the cutting interface.

Drilling operations also face challenges of heat build-up, especially near the drill tip. NF-MQL has demonstrated superior performance by improving chip evacuation and reducing tool wear, thereby enhancing hole quality and dimensional accuracy. Milling, often used for mold and die production, involves intermittent tool engagement, which makes lubrication critical. The introduction of NF-MQL in milling operations has led to significant improvements in surface finish, tool life, and overall process sustainability. Overall, literature reveals that NF-MQL can effectively enhance lubrication and cooling performance across various machining operations, making it a viable option for difficult-to-cut materials.

TABLE I. LITERATURE REVIEW OF PREVIOUS STUDIES

Ref. No.	Material Used	Properties/Characteristics	Applications
1 (2018), 5 (2017) 9 (2007), 18 (2017)	Inconel (718)	High-temperature strength	Aerospace industry, marine equipment, nuclear reactors,
2 (2021)	SS 304	Hardening Properties	Connecting rods, shafts, rams, axles
3 (2015), 6 (2018)	Al 6061	Strength-to-weight ratio	Structural applications, boats, furniture
4 (2015)	(700/3)	High strength-weight ratio,	Automotive
7 (2017)	AISI 4340	Higher Strength, Hardenability	Power Transmission gears and shafts
8 (2021)	60 Si2Mn	Hardenability	Heavy vehicles, tractors
10 (2009)	AISI 9310	Good strength and toughness	Aircraft engine gears and pinion shafts.

11 (2019)	90CrSi	Hardness, Wear resistance	Construction industry
12 (2017)	AISI 1020	Excellent Weldability,	Structural applications
13 (2010)	100Cr6	Moderate tensile strength	Automotive industry
14 (2020)	EN-GSJ 700-02	Higher mechanical properties	Cast press and stamping machine dies
15 (2020)	SKD 11	Good wear resistance	Cold-work dies, making
20 (2008)	EN8 Steel	Good surface hardness	Manufacturing of axles, shafts, and pins
24 (2020)	Alloy Steel 4140	High level of Hardness	High-wear applications
27 (2020)	Hastelloy C276	High strength	All-round engineering purposes
28 (2015)	Ti-6Al-4V	Excellent strength	Aerospace industry
29 (2014)	Nicrofer C263	High-temperature strength	Aircraft and industrial gas turbines.
30 (2019)	Inconel 625	Strength and toughness	Heat shields, gas turbine ducting,

III. NF-MQL For Sustainable Manufacturing

Conventional cutting fluids are formulated using base oils and additives to enhance cooling, lubrication, and corrosion resistance. However, the excessive use of these fluids leads to environmental hazards and operator health risks. To address these concerns, researchers have focused on sustainable alternatives such as dry machining, cryogenic cooling, and MQL. Among these, NF-MQL offers an optimal balance between cooling performance and eco-efficiency. Nanofluids—fluids enriched with nanoparticles like Al_2O_3 , CuO , MoS_2 , or SiO_2 —exhibit enhanced thermal conductivity, lubricity, and stability. When applied in MQL systems, these nanofluids form a nano-film at the tool–workpiece interface, reducing friction and temperature. Studies have shown that NF-MQL not only extends tool life but also lowers power consumption, cutting force, and tool wear.

Furthermore, NF-MQL supports sustainable manufacturing by drastically reducing lubricant usage and minimizing waste disposal issues. With careful selection of nanoparticle type, concentration, and base fluid, the tribological and heat transfer properties of NF-MQL can be optimized for specific machining applications. This approach aligns with global trends towards green manufacturing and energy efficiency.

IV. Futurscope On Machining Challenging Materials With NF-MQL

Despite promising results, NF-MQL technology is still in its early stages of industrial adoption. The machining of advanced materials such as titanium alloys, Inconel, and composites remains challenging due to complex interactions among multiple process parameters.

Future research should focus on the following key areas:

1. **Optimization of NF-MQL Parameters:** Systematic studies on spray characteristics, nozzle geometry, nanoparticle size, air pressure, and fluid flow rate to maximize cooling–lubrication efficiency.
2. **Nanofluid Properties:** Investigation of nanoparticle concentration, stability, and base fluid selection to enhance thermal and tribological performance.
3. **Machining Parameter Integration:** Comprehensive modelling of interactions between cutting speed, feed rate, and depth of cut with NF-MQL variables for predictive control
4. **Tool and Workpiece Considerations:** Development of coated and nanocomposite tools compatible with NF-MQL for improved performance in hard machining
5. **Industrial Implementation:** Assessing NF-MQL at production scale, particularly in small and medium enterprises (SMEs), to evaluate cost-effectiveness and reliability.
6. **Sustainability Metrics:** Formulating a standardized evaluation framework to quantify NF-MQL's impact on energy efficiency, environmental footprint, and machining quality.

V. Conclusions

From the literature, it is evident that MQL, particularly NF-MQL, offers a sustainable and high-performance alternative to conventional flood cooling systems. While MQL primarily provides lubrication with limited cooling capacity, its combination with nanofluids significantly improves heat dissipation and friction reduction. NF-MQL has shown excellent potential across various machining operations—turning, grinding, drilling, and milling—by improving tool life, surface finish, and process stability.

However, industrial implementation remains limited due to higher initial setup costs and the need for expertise in nanofluid preparation and delivery systems. To achieve broader acceptance, future research should aim to standardize NF-MQL formulations, establish clear sustainability metrics, and simplify system integration for industrial users. With continued advancements, NF-MQL could play a transformative role in achieving sustainable machining of difficult-to-cut materials, bridging the gap between high productivity and environmental responsibility.

TABLE II: SUMMARY OF MACHINING ON CHALLENGING MATERIALS UNDER MQL CONDITIONS

Research Summary on Grinding											
Ref. No.	Material	Machining	Input Parameters			Output Parameters					
			C S	FR	DOC	Ra	GF	TW	TL	CT	CDC
13 (2010)	100Cr6	CNC	√		√	√	√				
28 (2015)	Ti-6Al-4V	Grinder	√		√	√					√
51 (2013)	Inconel 751	Grinder	√		√	√	√			√	
52 (2008)	Ti-6Al-4V	Grinder	√		√	√	√				
53 (2013)	AISI 4340	Grinder	√		√	√			√		
54 (2013)	AA6061	Grinder	√		√	√	√				√
55 (2010)	EN8, M2	Grinder	√		√	√	√			√	
56 (2010)	100Cr6	Grinder	√		√	√	√				
57 (2009)	Hardened Steel	Grinder	√		√	√	√				
Research Summary on Turning											
Ref. No.	Material	Machining	Input Parameters			Output Parameters					
			C S	FR	DOC	Ra	CF	TW	TL	CT	CDC
1 (2018)	Inconel (718)	CNC Lathe	√	√	√					√	√
4(2015)	Ductile-Iron 700/3	Lathe	√	√	√	√		√			√
5 (2017)	Inconel (718)	CNC Lathe	√	√	√	√					
7 (2017)	AISI 4340	CNC Lathe	√	√	√	√		√			
9 (2007)	Inconel (718)	CNC Lathe	√	√	√	√			√		
10 (2009)	AISI 9310	Lathe	√	√		√			√	√	√
11 (2019)	90CrSi	Lathe	√			√	√				
12 (2017)	AISI 1020	Lathe		√	√	√				√	
18	In-	CNC	√	√	√	√					√

(2017)	conel (718)	C									
20 (2008)	EN8 Steel	Lath e	√	√	√	√	√	√	√		
24 (2020)	4140	CN C Lath e	√	√	√	√					
29 (2014)	Nico-fer C263	CN C Lath e	√	√	√	√				√	
42 (2013)	Ti-6Al-4V	CN C Lath e	√	√	√	√	√				
43 (2013)	AA6061	CN C Lath e	√	√	√		√				
Research Summary on Drilling											
Ref. No.	Material	Machining	Input Parameters			Output Parameters					
			C S	FR	DOC	Ra	CF	TW	TL	CT	CDC
2 (2021)	Stain. Steel 304	CN C	√	√	√	√			√		√
44 (2011)	In-conel 718	CN C	√	√		√					
45 (2006)	Ti-6Al-4V	CN C		√	√		√			√	
46 (2011)	A17075	Drilling	√	√		√				√	
47 (2007)	(A390.0)	CN C	√	√				√			√
48 (2010)	AISI-1040	CN C	√	√		√					
49 (2008)	Hardened Steel	CN C	√	√		√	√	√			
50 (2011)	B 319 Al Alloy	CN C	√	√					√		√
Research Summary on Milling											
Ref. No.	Material	Machining	Input Parameters			Output Parameters					
			C S	FR	DOC	Ra	CF	TW	TL	CT	CDC
3 (2015)	Alu-minium 6061	VM C		√	√	√					
6 (2018)	AA 6061-T6	VM C		√	√	√				√	
8 (2021)	60 Si2Mn	VM C	√	√		√	√				
14 (2020)	EN-GSJ 700-02	VM C	√	√	√	√		√			
15 (2020)	SKD 11	VM C		√		√					

27 (2020)	Has- telloy C276	VM C	√	√		√		√	√		
--------------	------------------------	---------	---	---	--	---	--	---	---	--	--

**TABLE III. RESEARCH SUMMARY OF PREVIOUS RESEARCH
 CONSIDERING MQL PROCESS PARAMETERS**

Ref. No.	Material	Machining	Base Fluid Used	Nano particles used	Nozzle Diameter	Nozzle Angle	Stand Off Distance	Air Flow Rate	Air Pressure	NP Concentration
5(2017)	Inconel (718)	CN C Lathe	Water Vapor		√		√	√	√	
(2018)	AA 6061-T6	VM C	Water		√	√		√		
7(2017)	AISI 4340	CN C Lathe	EG	MW CNT				√	√	
8(2021)	60 Si2Mn	VM C	Soybean Oil	Al2O3, MO S2				√	√	
10(2009)	AISI 9310	Lathe	Vegetable Oil							√
11(2019)	90CrSi	Lathe	Soybean Oil	Al2O3, MO S2						√
13(2010)	100Cr6	CN C	Castrol Oil			√	√	√	√	
14(2020)	EN-GSJ 700-02	VM C	Flooded Type	MO S2				√	√	
15(2020)	SKD 11	VM C	Soybean Oil					√	√	
27(2020)	Has-telloy C276	VM C	Cutting Oil	Al2O3						√
30	Inconel 625	CN C Milling	Vegetable Oil	MW CNT	√	√	√			

References

1. G. Kadam and R. Pawade, "Chip Deformation Aspects in Relative Eco-friendly HSM of Inconel 718", Procedia Manufacturing, vol. 20, pp. 35-40, 2018.
2. D. Subhedar, Y. Patel, B. Ramani and G. Patange, "An experimental investigation on the effect of Al2O3/ cutting oil-based Nano coolant for Minimum Quantity Lubrication drilling of SS 304", Cleaner Engineering and Technology, vol. 3, pp. 100-104, 2021.

3. Ojolo Sunday Joshua, Money Ochuko David, Ismail Oluwarotimi Sikiru, "Experimental Investigation of Cutting Parameters on Surface Roughness Prediction during End Milling of Aluminium 6061 under MQL (Minimum Quantity Lubrication)", *Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Automation*, pp. 1-13, 2015.
4. Sagar N. Sakharkar, Raju S. Pawade, Prakash K. Brahmankar, "Model Development and Sustainability Assessment of Minimum Quantity Lubrication Technique in Turning of 700/3 Austempered Ductile Iron", *Asian Journal of Convergence in Technology*, Volume II, Issue III, ISSN No.:2350-1146.
5. Ganesh S. Kadam, Raju S. Pawade, "Water Vapour as Eco-friendly Cutting Fluid -Parametric Explorations in HSM of Inconel 718", *Journal of Materials Science and Surface Engineering*, 5(7): 679-684.
6. W. Safiei, M. Rahman and S. Rusdan, "Experimental Investigation of MQL Optimum Parameters in End Milling of AA6061-T6 using Taguchi Method", *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, vol. 7, no. 435, p. 186, 2018.
7. P. Patole and V. Kulkarni, "Experimental investigation and optimisation of cutting parameters with multi-response characteristics in MQL turning of AISI 4340 using Nano fluid", *Cogent Engineering*, vol. 4, no. 1, p. 1303956, 2017.
8. T. Duc, T. Long and N. Tuan, "Performance Investigation of MQL Parameters Using Nano Cutting Fluids in Hard Milling", *Fluids*, vol. 6, no. 7, p. 248, 2021.
9. Y. Kamata and T. Obikawa, "High speed MQL finish-turning of Inconel 718 with different coated tools", *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 192-193, pp. 281-286, 2007.
10. M. Khan, M. Mithu and N. Dhar, "Effects of minimum quantity lubrication on turning AISI 9310 alloy steel using vegetable oil-based cutting fluid", *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 209, no. 15-16, pp. 5573-5583, 2009.
11. T. Duc, T. Long and T. Chien, "Performance Evaluation of MQL Parameters Using Al₂O₃ and MoS₂ Nanofluids in Hard Turning 90CrSi Steel", *Lubricants*, vol. 7, no. 5, p. 40, 2019.
12. D. Sonowal, D. Sarma, P. Barua and T. Nath, "Taguchi Optimisation of Cutting Parameters in Turning AISI 1020 MS with M2 HSS Tool", *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 225, p. 012186, 2017.
13. T. Tawakoli, M. Hadad and M. Sadeghi, "Influence of oil mist parameters on minimum quantity lubrication – MQL grinding process", *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, vol. 50, no. 6, pp. 521-531, 2010.
14. Bülent Çelik and Alaattin Kaçal, "Experimental Investigation on Nano MoS₂ Application in Milling of EN-GSJ 700-02 Cast Iron with Minimum Quantity Lubrication (MQL)", *Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research* Vol. 79, pp. 479-483, June 2020.
15. T. Duc and T. Long, "Effects of MQL and MQCL Parameters on Surface Roughness in Hard Milling of SKD 11 Tool Steel", *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 10, pp. 28-31, 2020.
16. Mark Velasquez and Patrick T. Hester, "An Analysis of Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Methods", *International Journal of Operations Research* Vol. 10, No. 2, 56-66, 2013.
17. P. Patole and V. Kulkarni, "Experimental investigation and optimisation of cutting parameters with multi-response characteristics in MQL turning of AISI 4340 using nano fluid", *Cogent Engineering*, Vol. 4, No. 1, p. 1303956, 2017.
18. M. Ali, A. Khalil, A. Azmi and H. Salleh, "Optimisation of Cutting Parameters for Surface Roughness under MQL, using Al₂O₃ Nanolubricant, during Turning

- of Inconel 718", IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering, vol. 226, p. 012067, 2017.
19. V. Sharma, G. Singh and K. Sørby, "A Review on Minimum Quantity Lubrication for Machining Processes", *Materials and Manufacturing Processes*, vol. 30, no. 8, pp. 935-953, 2014.
 20. D. Nageswara Rao and P. Vamsi Krishna, "The influence of solid lubricant particle size on machining parameters in turning", *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, vol. 48, no. 1, pp. 107-111, 2008.
 21. P. Patole and V. Kulkarni, "Optimisation of Process Parameters based on Surface Roughness and Cutting Force in MQL Turning of AISI 4340 using Nano Fluid", *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 104-112, 2018.
 22. P. Patole, V. Kulkarni and S. Bhatwadekar, "MQL Machining with nano fluid: a review", *Manufacturing Review*, vol. 8, p. 13, 2021.
 23. Siddharth Jeet and Sasmita Kar, "Review on Application of Minimum Quantity Lubrication (MQL) in Metal Turning Operations Using Conventional and Nano-Lubricants Based Cutting Fluids", *International Journal of Advanced Mechanical Engineering*, Volume 8, Number 1, pp. 63-70, 2018.
 24. Mr. Bharat Bhosale, Mr. Rahul Bhedasgaonkar, "Sustainable Machining of Alloy Steel 4140 with Minimum Quantity Lubrication (MQL)", *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, Volume: 07 Issue: 09, 2020.
 25. Mustafa Rifat, Md. Habibor Rahman, Debashish Das, "A Review on Application of Nanofluid MQL in Machining", *International Conference on Mechanical Engineering and Applied Science (ICMEAS 2017)*.
 26. Tran The Long and Tran Minh Duc, "The Characteristics and Application of Nanofluids in MQL and MQCL for Sustainable Cutting Processes", *Advances in Microfluidic Technologies for Energy and Environmental Applications*.
 27. F. Günan, T. Kivak, Ç. Yıldırım and M. Sarıkaya, "Performance evaluation of MQL with AL₂O₃ mixed nanofluids prepared at different concentrations in milling of Hastelloy C276 alloy", *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 10386-10400, 2020.
 28. Bhargavi A, Prashantha Kumar S T, "Application of Nano Cutting Fluid under Minimum Quantity Lubrication (MQL) Technique to Improve Grinding of Ti-6Al-4V - 4VAlloy", *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT)*, Vol-3, Issue 19 pp. 1-4, 2015.
 29. P Subhash Chandra Bose, C S P Rao², Kishore Jawale, "Role of MQL and Nano Fluids on the Machining of Nicrofer C263", *5th International and 26th All India Manufacturing Technology, Design and Research Conference (AIMTDR 2014) December 12th-14th, 2014, IIT Guwahati, Assam, India*, 2021.
 30. P. Singh, J. Dureja, H. Singh and M. S. Bhatti, "Nanofluid-based Minimum Quantity Lubrication (MQL) Face Milling of Inconel 625", *International Journal of Automotive and Mechanical Engineering*, Vol. 16, No. 3, pp. 6874-6888, 2019.
 31. B. Sen, M. Mia, G. Krolczyk, U. Mandal and S. Mondal, "Eco-Friendly Cutting Fluids in Minimum Quantity Lubrication Assisted Machining: A Review on the Perception of Sustainable Manufacturing", *International Journal of Precision Engineering and Manufacturing-Green Technology*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 249-280, 2019.
 32. R. Srikant, M. Prasad, M. Amrita, A. Sitaramaraju and P. Krishna, "Nanofluids as a potential solution for Minimum Quantity Lubrication: A review", *Proceedings*

- of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part B: Journal of Engineering Manufacture, vol. 228, no. 1, pp. 3-20, 2013.
33. E. Benedicto, D. Carou, E.M. Rubio, "Technical, Economic and Environmental Review of the Lubrication/Cooling Systems used in Machining Processes", Advances in Material & Processing Technologies Conference, Procedia Engineering 184 (2017) 99 – 116.
 34. Naser Ali, Joao A. Teixeira, and Abdulmajid Addali "A Review on Nanofluids: Fabrication, Stability, and Thermophysical Properties", Hindawi Journal of Nanomaterials, Volume 2018.
 35. A P Reverberi, D M D Addona, A A G Brozzone, R Teti, B Fabiano, "Nanotechnology in machining processes-Recent advances", CIRP Conference on Intelligent Computation in Manufacturing Engineering, Gulf of Naples, Italy, Procedia CIRP 79 (2019)3-8.
 36. H. Hegab, B. Darras, H A. Kishawy, "Sustainability Assessment of Machining with Nano-Cutting Fluids", North American Manufacturing Research Conference, NAMRC 46, Texas, USA, Procedia Manufacturing 26 (2018) 245-254.
 37. R. Saidura, K. Y. Leongb, H. A. Mohammad, "A review on applications and challenges of nanofluids", Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews 15 (2011) 1646–1668.
 38. Kumaran Kadirgama, "Nanofluid as an Alternative Coolant in Machining: A Review", Journal of Advanced Research in Fluid Mechanics and Thermal Sciences 69, Issue 1 (2020) 163-173.
 39. Y. Shokoohi, E. Shekarian, "Application of Nanofluids in Machining Processes - A Review", Journal of Nanoscience and Technology 2(1) (2016) 59–63
 40. Kaufui V.Wong and Omar De Leon, "Applications of Nanofluids: Current and Future", Hindawi Publishing Corporation, Advances in Mechanical Engineering, Volume 2010.
 41. Samarpan Deb Majumder, Ankit Das, "A Short Review of Organic Nanofluids: Preparation, Surfactants, and Applications", Frontiers in Materials, Vol. 8, April 2021.
 42. Liu, Z.; Xu, J.; Han, S.; Chen, M., "A coupling method of response surfaces (CRSM) for cutting parameters optimization in machining titanium alloy under minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) condition", International Journal of Precision Engineering and Manufacturing 2013, 14, 693–702.
 43. Shashidhara, Y.M.; Jayaram, S.R., "Experimental determination of cutting power for turning and material removal rate for drilling of AA 6061-T6 using vegetable oils as cutting fluid", Advances in Tribology 2013, 2013, 1–7
 44. Rahim, E.A.; Sasahara, H., "An analysis of surface integrity when drilling Inconel 718 using palm oil and synthetic ester under MQL condition", Machining Science and Technology 2011, 15, 76–90.
 45. Zeilmann, R.P.; Weingaertner, W.L., "Analysis of temperature during drilling of Ti6Al4V with minimal quantity of lubricant", Journal of Materials Processing Technology 2006, 179, 124–127.
 46. Kilickap, E.; Huseyinoglu, M.; Ozel, C., "Empirical study regarding the effects of minimum quantity lubricant utilization on performance characteristics in the drilling of Al", Journal of the Brazilian Society of Mechanical Sciences and Engineering 2011, XXXIII, 52–57.

47. Jayal, A.D.; Balaji, A.K.; Sesek, R.; Engineering, M.; Lake, S, "Machining performance and health effects of cutting fluid application in drilling of A3900 cast aluminum alloy", *Journal of Manufacturing Processes* 2007, 9, 137–146.
48. Ahsan, N.A.M.M.; Kibria, G.M.; Ahmed, R.M.; Islam, A.M.; Hossain, M.M., "Performance evaluation of Minimum Quantity Lubrication (MQL) in drilling operation", *International Conference on Mechanical, Industrial and Energy Engineering*, Khulna, Bangladesh, December 23–24 2010; 1–5.
49. Tasdelen, B.; Wikblom, T.; Ekered, S., "Studies on minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) and air cooling at drilling", *Journal of Materials Processing Technology* 2008, 200, 339–346.
50. Fox-Rabinovich, G.; Dasch, J.M.; Wagg, T.; Yamamoto, K.; Veldhuis, S.; Dosbaeva, G.K.; Tauhiduzzaman, M., "Cutting performance of different coatings during minimum quantity lubrication drilling of aluminum silicon B319 cast alloy", *Surface and Coatings Technology* 2011, 205, 4107–4116.
51. Balan, A.S.S.; Vijayaraghavan, L.; Krishnamurthy, R., "Minimum quantity lubricated grinding of Inconel 751 alloy", *Materials and Manufacturing Processes* 2013, 28, 430–435.
52. Sadeghi, M.H.; Haddad, M.J.; Tawakoli, T.; Emami, M., "Minimal quantity lubrication-MQL in grinding of Ti-6Al-4V titanium alloy", *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology* 2008, 44, 487–500.
53. Silva, L.R.; Correia, E.C.S.; Brandão, J.R.; De A Vila, R.F., "Environmentally friendly manufacturing: Behavior analysis of minimum quantity of lubricant-MQL in grinding process", *Journal of Cleaner Production* 2013.
54. Hadad, M.; Hadi, M., "An investigation on surface grinding of hardened stainless steel S34700 and aluminum alloy AA6061 using minimum quantity of lubrication (MQL) technique", *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology* 2013, 68, 2145–2158.
55. Barczak, L.M.; Batako, A.D.L.; Morgan, M.N, "A study of plane surface grinding under minimum quantity lubrication (MQL) conditions", *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture* 2010, 50, 977–985.
56. Tawakoli, T.; Hadad, M.J.; Sadeghi, M.H., "Investigation on minimum quantity lubricant-MQL grinding of 100Cr6 hardened steel using different abrasive and coolant-lubricant types", *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture* 2010, 50, 698–708.
57. Tawakoli, T.; Hadad, M.J.; Sadeghi, M.H.; Daneshi, A.; Stockert, S.; Rasifard, "An experimental investigation of the effects of workpiece and grinding parameters on minimum quantity lubrication- MQL grinding", *International Journal of Machine Tools & Manufacture* 2009, 49, 924–932.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

NF	- Nano fluid
NP	- Nano particle
MQL	- Minimum Quantity Lubrication
CS	- Cutting Speed
FR	- Feed Rate
DOC	- Depth of Cut
Ra	- Surface Roughness
GF	- Grinding Force

CF - Cutting Force
TW - Tool Wear
TL - Tool Life
CT - Cutting Temperature
CDC - Chip Deformation Coefficient
MWCNT - Multi-Wall Carbon Nano Tube
 Al_2O_3 - Aluminium Dioxide
CuO - Copper Oxide
 MoS_2 - Molybdenum Disulfide
 SiO_2 - Silicon Dioxide

IEEE conference templates contain guidance text for composing and formatting conference papers. Please ensure that all template text is removed from your conference paper prior to submission to the conference. Failure to remove template text from your paper may result in your paper not being published.